

INNO4CFIs

Regenerative Carbon Farming

D1.1 DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

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Deliverable lead	Fondazione E. Amaldi
Author(s)	Eleonora Lombardi (FEA), Valerio Roscani (FEA)
Contact	eleonora.lombardi@fondazioneamaldi.it
Reviewer	Alessandro Zecca (Planet), Elisabetta Meconcelli (Treedom), Maxym Malynowsky (Space4Good), Andrea Boffi (AB Corporation), Andreas Ellenberger (Circonnact), Marta Plaza (USAL), (NTUA), Erika Albero & Ruth Manzanares (AINIA), Joaquim Halen (NOVOBIOM), Tomáš Vitek (TREEO), (RANCHO), Nika Levikov (F6S)
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The INNO4CFIs Consortium Partners are the following:

Participant No	Short Name	Legal name	Country
1	FEA	Fondazione E. Amaldi	IT
2	Planet	PLANET DI VILLA ALESSANDRO & C SAS	IT
3	Treedom srl	TREEDOM SRL SOCIETA' BENEFIT	IT
4	Space4Good	SPACE4GOOD B.V.	NL
5	CNR	CONSIGLIO NAZIONALE DELLE RICERCHE	IT
6	F6S IE	F6S NETWORK IRELAND LIMITED	IE
7	AB Corporation	AB CORPORATION	BE
8	Circonnect	VEREIN ZUR FÖRDERUNG DER REGENERATIVEN KREISLAUFWIRTSCHAFT	AT
9	USAL	UNIVERSIDAD DE SALAMANCA	ES
10	NTUA	ETHNICON METSOVION POLYTECHNION	EL
11	AINIA	AINIA	ES
12	NOVOBIOM	NOVOBIOM	BE
13	TreeO	FAIRVENTURES DIGITAL GMBH	DE
14	RANCHO	RANCHO GUARENA HNOS OLEA LOSA SL	ES

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The concept of INNO4CFIs has the following objectives:

1. promoting an innovative **Carbon Farm Technology Platform** as an outcome of the integration of 4 different technologies, tree planting practices and validating them in 4 different innovation ecosystems (GR, IT, ES, BE – 3 out of 4 from low/moderate innovative regions) to increase CO₂ uptake while promoting crucial environmental co-benefits such as sustainable freshwater production, dryland and soil restoration and, biodiversity promotion, via a novel business model resulting from a combination of different technologies owned by the partners of the INNO4CFIs consortium.

2. **funding highly innovative carbon farming technologies** with minimum TRL6 promoted by SMEs located in i3-eligible countries and related innovation ecosystems, through a cascade funding system, thus improving European regional areas that have been selected to be at the forefront of European market innovation and enriching the competitive advantage of the targeted territories.

The **Data Management Plan (DMP)** of INNO4CFIs describes the types of data that will be produced, collected and/or processed within the project and how this data will be handled during and after the project, i.e. the standards that will be used, how data will be exploited and shared (for verification or reuse), and in which way data will be preserved. The elaboration of the DMP will allow INNO4CFIs partners to address all issues related to data protection, including ethical concerns and security protection strategy. Moreover, each beneficiary must ensure open access to all peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to its results: these publications will be made available through the public section of the INNO4CFIs website. All these aspects have been taken into account in the elaboration of the DMP.

Data management is a crucial issue for research and innovation projects and key for the understanding of what to do with the data generated and how to preserve them or make them available for other researchers too. These datasets cover the collected stakeholder contacts, public security services and digital security solutions. Furthermore, the empirical research will generate data from expert interviews, focus groups and workshops. Additionally, the validation of the INNO4CFIs solution will also generate data.

The present Data Management Plan is the report that describes the procedures of data collection, storing and processing of INNO4CFIs, including the ethical concerns that could affect the project.

INTRODUCTION

Research and innovation projects such as INNO4CFIs usually generate large sets of data. Depending on the discipline, the data could come from social science research, laboratory testing, field studies or observations. However, it often remains unclear and uncertain what will happen with the data after they are analysed, and the project is finished. Furthermore, a lot of datasets are potentially interesting also for other researchers, but because they are either stored on a local server or miss crucial meta-data (or both), their potential value cannot be exploited. Hence, researchers need to think about the data that they will produce at the beginning of the research – and this is exactly the purpose of the DMP.

With this DMP, the INNO4CFIs consortium aims to provide an analysis of the main elements of the data management policy that will be used in the project and by the partners with regard to the project research data. The DMP covers the complete research data life cycle. It describes the types of research data that will be generated or collected during the project, the standards that will be used, how the research data will be preserved and what parts of the datasets will be shared for verification or reuse.

The DMP is a living document, which will evolve during the lifespan of the project, particularly whenever significant changes arise such as dataset updates or changes in partnership policies. It includes an overview of the datasets to be produced by the project and the specific conditions that are related to them. Although this report already covers a broad range of aspects related to INNO4CFIs data management, an intermediary internal check will be operated on particular issues such as data interoperability and practical data management procedures implemented by the project consortium. A second release of the DPM is foreseen in M18 (ref. Del. 1.2) while a final release of the DPM is planned at the end of the project in M36 (ref. Del. 1.3).

The first section of the DMP offers an overview of the datasets which will be produced in the INNO4CFIs project. It describes the origins of the data as well as the formats, the allocation and the specific WPs. Furthermore, it highlights the purpose of the collection as well as information on the utility. Section 2 points out which data will be made openly accessible, and which won't – including detailed justifications for the reasons. This is particularly relevant for the primary data that will be collected as part of the empirical research. The section also provides details on the data repositories or other locations, where the data will be stored. Section 3 analyses other research outputs that may be generated or re-used throughout the project. Section 4 highlights the main aspects regarding the costs of accessibility, whereas Section 5 discusses the data security issues. Finally, Section 6 focuses on the ethics review while the final section provides an outlook on the open issues and questions.

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LIST OF ACRONYMS

ACRONYM	MEANING
DPO	DATA PROTECTION OFFICER
DMP	DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN
Dx.y.	DELIVERABLE Y OF WORK PACKAGE X
DEL.	DELIVERABLE
EU	EUROPEAN UNION
FAIR	FINDABLE, ACCESSIBLE, INTEROPERABLE, REUSABLE
GDPR	GENERAL DATA PROTECTION REGULATION
IPR	INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY RIGHTS
OPENAIRE	OPEN ACCESS INFRASTRUCTURE FOR RESEARCH IN EUROPE
OPENDOAR	DIRECTORY OF OPEN ACCESS REPOSITORIES
ROAR	REGISTRY OF OPEN ACCESS REPOSITORIES
SMEs	SMALL AND MEDIUM-SIZED ENTERPRISES
WP	WORK PACKAGE

1. DATA SUMMARY

The following section aims to review the scope of the data management for the INNO4CFIs project with a focus on the purposes, objectives, types, formats, size, and origin of the data either generated or re-used. INNO4CFIs will collect and generate the users' data respecting the standards set by national legislation and the Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation). The INNO4CFIs consortium is committed to processing data fairly and lawfully.

The data will be collected based on surveys, questionnaires, interviews, recordings, desk research, in situ data collection, laboratory testing, field studies or observations.

On the one hand, the data derived from desk research will be elaborated and shared with entrepreneurial ecosystems, institutions, policy makers, and innovation actors in the form of publications, in the form of a public guideline on specific needs for low/moderate innovation regions, and of INNO4CFIs guidelines on the project's standard operating procedures. Also, the recordings of the events, interviews or meetings for promotional purposes will be openly shared for communication and dissemination purposes.

On the other hand, the data derived from surveys, questionnaires, interviews, in situ data collection, laboratory testing, field studies or observations should remain internal in order to avoid sharing any property rights within the market and/or with other companies. The collected data can be used only by the partners of INNO4CFIs exclusively for the deployment of the activities foreseen by the project.

The following table presents the types of data that will be collected, their description and purpose as well as their utility for the implementation of the project.

Table 1: Table presenting the data collected by the project, their description and purpose.

#	DATA TYPE	ORIGIN	DESCRIPTION AND PURPOSE	UTILITY OUTSIDE THE PROJECT
1	STAKEHOLDERS CONTACTS COLLECTION	SURVEYS, QUESTIONNAIRES, AND INTERVIEWS	<u>DESCRIPTION:</u> THE DATA CONTAINS INFORMATION ON THE MAIN STAKEHOLDERS OF INNO4CFIs ALONG WITH THE MAJOR IDENTIFIED STAKEHOLDER GROUPS, SUCH AS: ASSOCIATIONS, UNIVERSITIES, RESEARCH CENTERS, CARBON FARMING EXPERTS, INCUBATORS, ACCELERATORS, INVESTORS, SMES, LARGE AND PRIVATE COMPANIES, PUBLIC AUTHORITIES, CLUSTERS, POLICYMAKERS, FARMERS AND AGRICULTURAL COMMUNITIES,	THE DATA COULD BE ON THE ONE HAND USEFUL FOR RESEARCH AND MONITORING PURPOSES AS THEY COMPRISE A LARGE PART OF THE ENTREPRENEURIAL ECOSYSTEMS. ON THE OTHER HAND, THE DATA MIGHT ALSO BE INTERESTING

			<p>ENVIRONMENTAL AGENCIES AND NGOs, AND OTHER INITIATIVES AND INDUSTRY FIGURES. THE CONTACT INFORMATION THAT IS COLLECTED INCLUDES THE NAME, INSTITUTIONAL AFFILIATION, POSITION, EMAIL ADDRESS, PHONE NUMBER, OFFICE ADDRESS. THE ASSOCIATED DATA TYPES WILL BE CAPTURED BOTH BY TRADITIONAL TOOLS AND BY TAKING ADVANTAGE OF THE PARTNERS' REPOSITORY.</p> <p><u>PURPOSE:</u> THE COLLECTION WILL BE USED FOR INNO4CFIs CONTEXT ANALYSIS, I.E. INVENTORY OF THE SUCCESS CASES AND GO-TO-BUSINESS SCENARIO (DEL. 2.1 AND SUBSEQUENT UPDATES), THE REPORT ON SPECIFIC NEEDS FOR LOW AND MODERATE INNOVATION REGIONS (DEL. 2.2 AND SUBSEQUENT UPDATES), THE KPIS INVENTORY (DEL. 2.5); FOR THE STAKEHOLDERS GUIDELINES (DEL. 6.4), THE END USERS QUESTIONNAIRES (DEL. 6.5); FOR THE EXPLOITATION, IPR AND BUSINESS MODEL ROADMAPS (DEL. 7.1), THE STANDARDIZATION ROADMAP INCLUDING FTO ANALYSIS (DEL. 7.2 AND ASSESSMENT OF THE MARKET READINESS (DEL. 7.3); QUALITY ASSURANCE PLAN (DEL. 9.1), MONITORING AND EVALUATION REPORT (DEL 9.2 AND SUBSEQUENT UPDATES). IT ALSO PROVIDES THE BASIS FOR THE DISSEMINATION OF THE PROJECT AND FOR PROMOTING THE INNO4CFIs SOLUTION (DEL. 10.1 AND SUBSEQUENT UPDATES) AND CONTAINS INFORMATION OF PARTNERS OF DEL. 10.5, MoU FOR FURTHER EXPLOITATION.</p>	<p>FOR THE PRIVATE SECTOR AS TARGET GROUPS OF THEIR PRODUCTS AND FOR BOOSTING PARTNERSHIP AGREEMENTS WITH WORLDWIDE STAKEHOLDERS.</p>
2	TARGET USERS CONTACTS COLLECTION		<p><u>DESCRIPTION:</u> THE DATA COLLECTED DURING THE INVOLVEMENT PHASE OF THE TARGET USERS WILL BE INTEGRATED WITH THE DATA THAT WILL BE PRODUCED DURING THE IMPLEMENTATION OF THE INNO4CFIs SOLUTIONS. THIS</p>	<p>THE COLLECTION OF THIS DATA IS A CRUCIAL STEP TO THE FUTURE PROJECT DEVELOPMENT AS IT WILL HELP BUILD THE FINAL SERVICES</p>

			<p>PROCEDURE WILL ALLOW THE INNO4CFIs CONSORTIUM TO ANALYSE AND SHARE DATA IN ORDER TO IMPROVE THE FUNCTIONALITY, INCREASE THE USABILITY OF THE SOLUTIONS, AND IDENTIFY THE REQUIREMENTS OF THE TARGET USERS FOR THE SOLUTIONS OPTIMIZATION AND VALIDATION OF THE OVERALL INNO4CFIs METHODOLOGY AT EUROPEAN LEVEL. IN ADDITION, FEASIBILITY STUDIES, MARKET STUDIES, AND RESEARCH RESULTS WILL PROVIDE INFORMATION ON END-USER NEEDS AND REQUIREMENTS FOR THE INNO4CFIs INNOVATIVE APPROACH.</p> <p><u>PURPOSE:</u> THE COLLECTION IS EXPLOITED TO GET AN OVERVIEW OF INNO4CFIs SOLUTIONS' PERFORMANCE AND TO IMPROVE IT ACCORDING TO BOTH END-USERS AND THE STAKEHOLDERS NEEDS. CONCERNING THE FORMER, DATA WILL BE NECESSARY FOR ENHANCING THE PROPER READABILITY AND USABILITY OF THE DEVELOPED SOLUTIONS.</p>	<p>CLOSER TO THE ACTUAL END-USERS AND STAKEHOLDERS' NEEDS.</p>
3	<p>BUSINESS AND FINANCIAL DATA OF THE TARGET USERS TO ACCESS CASCADE FUNDING OPPORTUNITIES</p>		<p><u>DESCRIPTION:</u> DURING THE IMPLEMENTATION OF THE INNO4CFIs SERVICES, THE TARGET USERS WILL BE REQUESTED TO SHARE THEIR BUSINESS DATA FOR THE SELECTION AS RECIPIENT OF THE FSTP. THIS WILL BE DONE BY ELABORATING AN OPEN CALL DOCUMENT KIT AND THIRD-PARTY FINANCIAL RULES (DEL. 8.1).</p> <p><u>PURPOSE:</u> THESE DATA WILL BE NEEDED TO SELECT THE COMPANIES TO ACCESS THE FSTP PROCEDURES AND OPPORTUNITIES AND TO ELABORATE DEL OPEN CALLS REPORTS (DEL 8.2, DEL 8.3) AS WELL AS THE ANALYTICS ON THE SUBMITTED PROPOSALS AND SELECTED PROJECTS (DEL 8.4).</p>	<p>THESE DATA ARE KEY FOR THE UNDERSTANDING OF THE TECHNICAL, BUSINESS, FINANCIAL AND COMMERCIAL STATUS OF THE SMEs FOR THE ALLOCATION OF THE FSTP.</p>

4	NON-SENSITIVE PUBLISHABLE DATA (PUBLICATIONS)	DESK RESEARCH AND PUBLIC RECORDINGS	<p><u>DESCRIPTION:</u> FOLLOWING THE IMPLEMENTATION OF THE PROJECT'S ACTIVITIES, THE INNO4CFIs CONSORTIUM WILL BE ABLE TO COLLECT A SET OF DATA BASED ON DESK RESEARCH AND PUBLIC RECORDINGS. THIS WILL BE DONE THROUGH OPEN SOURCE DATA COLLECTION AND MATCHMAKING WITH THE DATA DERIVED FROM THE OUTCOMES OF THE PROJECT DEVELOPMENT.</p> <p><u>PURPOSE:</u> THESE DATA ARE NEEDED FOR COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION PURPOSES IN ORDER TO BOOST THE PROMOTION AND OUTREACH OF THE PROJECT SERVICES AS WELL AS OF THE PROJECT OUTCOMES.</p>	THE DATA COULD BE ON THE ONE HAND USEFUL FOR RESEARCH AND EXPLOITATION PURPOSES AS THEY WILL BE SHARED WITH A WIDER TARGET AUDIENCE. ON THE OTHER HAND, THE DATA ARE INTERESTING FOR THE PUBLIC AND PRIVATE SECTORS AS TARGET GROUPS OF THE PROJECT'S OUTPUTS.
5	RECORDINGS OF THE EVENTS, INTERVIEWS OR MEETINGS		<p><u>DESCRIPTION:</u> THIS WILL BE DONE THROUGH OPEN DATA COLLECTION AND RECORDING OF THE EVENTS IN WHICH THE STAKEHOLDERS AND THE TARGET USERS WILL PARTICIPATE.</p> <p><u>PURPOSE:</u> THESE DATA ARE NEEDED FOR COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION PURPOSES IN ORDER TO BOOST THE PROMOTION AND OUTREACH OF THE PROJECT SERVICES AS WELL AS OF THE PROJECT OUTCOMES BASED ON THE EXPLOITATION OF DIRECT FEEDBACK AND CONTACT WITH THE PARTICIPANTS.</p>	THESE DATA COULD BE SHARED AND MAINSTREAMED ON SEVERAL PUBLIC PLATFORMS AND USED AS A WAY TO DISSEMINATE THE NEEDS AND OPPORTUNITIES OFFERED TO THE EUROPEAN ENTREPRENEURIAL ECOSYSTEMS ESPECIALLY IN LOW/MODERATE INNOVATION COUNTRIES.
6	DATA REPOSITORY FOR INTERNAL PROJECT MANAGEMENT (DELIVERABLES, REPORTS, RESULTS, MAILING LIST OF CONTACTS)	PROJECT IMPLEMENTATION	<p><u>DESCRIPTION:</u> THE INTERNAL MANAGEMENT OF THE PROJECT INNO4CFIs FORESEES THE COLLECTION OF DATA NEEDED TO DELIVER THE NEEDED OUTPUTS FOR PROJECT IMPLEMENTATION AND MONITORING.</p> <p><u>PURPOSE:</u> INTERNAL PROJECT MANAGEMENT BASED ON THE ELABORATION OF THE REQUESTED DELIVERABLES, REPORTS, AND</p>	THE DATA FROM THE REPOSITORY OF THE PROJECT MANAGEMENT HAVE AN INTERNAL USE ONLY UNTIL THEY ARE MADE PUBLIC IN THE CORRECT FORM (E.G. PUBLIC DELIVERABLES).

			RESULTS BY THE EUROPEAN COMMISSION. THIS ALSO ENTAILS THE RECORDING OF WORKING EMAILS AND SHARING INFORMATION ON THE PEOPLE WORKING INSIDE THE CONSORTIUM.	
7	VALIDATION DATA		<p><u>DESCRIPTION:</u> IN ORDER TO REDUCE THE CHANCE OF ERROR AND INCREASE THE SUCCESS OF THE BUSINESS OPPORTUNITY, INNO4CFIs WILL PERFORM ACTIVITIES ORIENTED TO DESIGN THE BUSINESS PLAN OF THE PROJECT FOR EXPLOITATION PURPOSES BASED ON A CONTINUOUS VALIDATION OF DATA.</p> <p><u>PURPOSE:</u> THE VALIDATION PROVIDES THE BASIS FOR IMPROVING AND RELEASING THE FINAL SOLUTIONS.</p>	THE DATA FROM THE VALIDATION OF IMPLEMENTED SERVICES MAINLY HAVE AN INTERNAL USE FOR IMPROVING THE SOLUTIONS AND FOR THE LESSONS LEARNED AND BUSINESS PLAN ELABORATION.
8	ENVIRONMENTAL, SOCIAL AND ECONOMIC IMPACT	IN SITU DATA COLLECTION, LABORATORY TESTING, FIELD STUDIES OR OBSERVATIONS	<p><u>DESCRIPTION:</u> IT WILL BE POSSIBLE TO PROVIDE FIRST-HAND INFORMATION NEEDED TO PERFORM AN INTEGRATED SUSTAINABILITY ASSESSMENT VIA FIELD STUDIES, USAGE SCENARIOS, MARKET STUDIES AND INDUSTRIAL RESEARCH OUTPUTS. IN THIS REGARD, DATA ABOUT THE IMPACT ON THE ECOSYSTEM AND SOCIOECONOMIC CONTEXT WILL BE COLLECTED BY CONSIDERING CRUCIAL CRITERIA.</p> <p><u>PURPOSE:</u> TO PROVIDE PROS AND CONS OF THE INNO4CFIs SOLUTION</p>	THIS DATA IS USEFUL TO IDENTIFY HOW INNO4CFIs AFFECT ENVIRONMENTAL CONSERVATION AND THE ECOSYSTEM, WHILE PRODUCING SIGNIFICANT COST/TIME BENEFITS.
9	TECHNOLOGY INTEGRATION		<p><u>DESCRIPTION:</u> ACCORDING TO THE ANALYSIS CARRIED OUT IN THE PHASE OF WEFE NEXUS AND STAKEHOLDERS ANALYSIS AND ASSESSMENT, THE TECHNOLOGY PARTNERS WILL DEVELOP A SPECIFIC STRATEGY FOR ENABLING A BETTER MONITOR AND CONTROL OF THE KEY PARAMETERS AND DATA COLLECTION AND UTILIZATION FROM:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - MANGROVE TECHNOLOGY PLATFORM - SOIL REMEDIATION 	THE DATA FROM THE TECHNOLOGY INTEGRATION ARE FUNDAMENTAL FOR THE CREATION OF THE TECHNOLOGY SOLUTION.

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - CO2 SEQUESTRATION FOR FARMING PROCESSES - ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE AND REMOTE SENSING - GREEN BLOCKCHAIN AND CARBON CREDITS <p><u>PURPOSE:</u> THE TECHNOLOGY INTEGRATION PROVIDES THE ELABORATION OF A SYSTEM CLOSED AND COMPOSED OF KEY ELEMENTS FOR THE ELABORATION OF THE CARBON FARMING TECHNOLOGY PLATFORM.</p>	
10	QUALITATIVE AND QUANTITATIVE RESOURCE INCREASE	QUALITY ASSESSMENT	<p><u>DESCRIPTION:</u> THE VALIDATION IN THE LIVING LABS WILL INCREASE THE AVAILABILITY OF QUALITATIVE AND QUANTITATIVE DATA CONCERNING THE EFFICIENCY PERFORMANCE OF THE TECHNOLOGY AND ITS DEGREE OF ADAPTABILITY TO DIVERSE SITUATIONS AND OPERATION CONTEXTS. PARTICULARLY, QUALITY AND QUANTITY CONTROLS WILL BE CARRIED OUT IN TERMS OF ENVIRONMENTAL AND TECHNICAL IMPACTS.</p> <p><u>PURPOSE:</u> ALL COLLECTED DATA WILL SERVE AS A TOOL TO GUIDE THE MONITORING PLANT FUNCTIONALITY AND PRODUCTIVITY AND CARBON STORAGE (TASK 6.5); BIODIVERSITY ASSESSMENT AND CREDIT VALIDATION PROCESS (TASK 6.6); B2B SELLING OF THE TREES THROUGH THE TREEDOM PLATFORM (TASK 6.8)</p>	THE INFORMATION PROVIDED IN THE DATA IS IMPORTANT FOR THE INNO4CFIs ITSELF AS WELL AS FOR THE ENTIRE CHAIN OF STAKEHOLDERS.
11	VALIDATION CYCLES DATA		<p><u>DESCRIPTION:</u> IN ORDER TO REDUCE THE CHANCE OF ERROR, INNO4CFIs WILL PERFORM ACTIVITIES ORIENTED TO DESIGN THE DATA VALIDATION PROCESS FOR EACH STATISTICAL DOMAIN: A LIST OF SUITABLE AND EFFECTIVE VALIDATION RULES WILL BE SET UP. SUBSEQUENTLY, THE VALIDATION RULES WILL BE DESCRIBED IN COMMON SYNTAX, FORMALISED, TESTED AND REFINED.</p> <p><u>PURPOSE:</u> THE VALIDATION PROVIDES</p>	THE DATA FROM THE VALIDATION IMPLEMENTED TECHNOLOGIES DO MAINLY HAVE AN INTERNAL USE FOR IMPROVING THE SOLUTIONS AND FOR THE LESSONS LEARNED.

			THE BASIS FOR IMPROVING AND RELEASING THE FINAL SOLUTIONS.	
12	MULTI-PARAMETERS FIELD DATA ACQUISITION		<p><u>DESCRIPTION:</u> INNO4CFIs WILL IDENTIFY THE PARAMETERS TO BE MONITORED FOR THE CARBON FARMING ASSESSMENT AND ALL THE PROCESSES TO GATHER, ANALYSE AND SHARE DATA. THE RELEVANT ANALYSIS WILL BE INTEGRATED AND FINALLY DATA WILL BE SHARED WITH STAKEHOLDERS IN ORDER TO BOOST PROJECT ADAPTABILITY AND REPLICABILITY.</p> <p><u>PURPOSE:</u> THE PRIMARY PURPOSE IS TO SUCCESSFULLY INTEGRATE DATA REGARDING THE TECHNOLOGIES' EFFICIENCY IN ORDER TO BOOST THE ADOPTION OF THE FINAL TECHNOLOGY BY RELEVANT STAKEHOLDERS AND CUSTOMERS.</p>	CRUCIAL FOR THE INTERACTION OF DATA FLOWS AND DECISION-MAKING PROCESSES BY THE ACTIONS INVOLVED IN THE NATIONAL, EUROPEAN, INTERNATIONAL SCENARIO BOTH AT PRIVATE AND PUBLIC LEVEL.

A data repository will be managed by FEA for storing common data, results, reports, and deliverables. Confidential information about businesses and their products with a market/business exploitation potential will be restrictedly accessible to INNO4CFIs partners. Non-sensitive publishable data will be shared and made accessible to the scientific community for verification, reuse (e.g. in publications), cross-validation, and other research purposes. The INNO4CFIs consortium strongly supports Open Access policies for any kind of scientific document, including monographs, books, journal papers, and conference proceedings. In order to comply with Open Access requirements, the INNO4CFIs consortium will ensure free access to all its publications. To this aim, an online archive will be selected through either the Open Access Infrastructure for Research in Europe (OpenAIRE) service, the Registry of Open Access Repositories (ROAR) or the Directory of Open Access Repositories (OpenDOAR).

2. FAIR DATA

2.1 MAKING DATA FINDABLE, INCLUDING PROVISIONS OF METADATA

INNO4CFIs will adopt a proactive strategy for managing research data and other research outputs, in line with the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable).

According to table 1, the following datasets have been identified:

1. User-related data (#1, #2, #3)

2. Research data (#4, #5, #6, #7)
3. Impact data (#8, #9, #10, #11, #12)

The following table presents the intersection of identified datasets with the level of accessibility and type of availability:

Table 2: Table presenting the intersection of identified datasets with the level of accessibility and type of availability

#	DATA TYPE	LOCATION	LEVEL OF ACCESSIBILITY	TYPE OF AVAILABILITY AND REQUIRED SOFTWARE TOOLS	INFORMATION ON METADATA AND ADDITIONAL DATA INFORMATION
1	USER-RELATED DATA	INNO4CFIs INTERNAL DATABASE	SENSITIVE	FILTERABLE AND SEARCHABLE DATABASE; CAN BE ACCESSED WITH A STATE-OF-THE-ART WEB-BROWSER.	NO METADATA NEEDED.
2	RESEARCH DATA	INNO4CFIs PUBLIC DOCUMENTS	PUBLIC	RESEARCH PAPERS, REPORTS, STUDYING DOCUMENTS, RECORDINGS	NO METADATA NEEDED.
3	IMPACT DATA	INNO4CFIs INTERNAL DATABASE	INTERNAL USE	RESEARCH PAPERS, REPORTS, STUDYING DOCUMENTS, BUSINESS PLAN, IPRs.	NO METADATA NEEDED.

Metadata could be created according to the data identified through WPs. Task leaders will collect data from each task – the data will be reviewed and approved if it is identified as appropriate for open access. This process will be carried out on an ongoing basis to facilitate the publication of appropriate data as soon as possible. The aim is to avoid any possible conflicts between open access and IPRs issues.

2.2 MAKING DATA ACCESSIBLE

INNO4CFIs is committed to making data accessible as presented in the table below. In case datasets are unavailable for public sharing according to a specific reason, a justification is provided or an alternative solution is identified.

Table 3: Table presenting the public sharing availability of the datasets

#	DATA TYPE	DATA OPENLY AVAILABLE (Y/N)	JUSTIFICATION	ALTERNATIVE SOLUTION
1	STAKEHOLDERS CONTACTS COLLECTION	N	THE COLLECTION OF THESE TYPES OF CONTACTS COME FROM PROFESSIONALS' PUBLICLY AVAILABLE DATABASES. HOWEVER, THE INNO4CFIs CONSORTIUM IS NOT ENTITLED TO PUBLISH THEM DUE TO POTENTIAL MISUSE CAUSED	THE STATISTICAL INFORMATION ON THE STAKEHOLDER DATA (SUCH AS HOW MANY, FROM WHICH COUNTRIES, WHICH PROFESSIONS, ETC.) CAN BE INTEGRATED IN A DETAILED REPORT IN AN AGGREGATED WAY TO AVOID INDIVIDUAL SPECIFICATION. ALSO, IF REQUESTED BY AN EXTERNAL

			BY AUTOMATED SPAM PROGRAMS.	PARTY OR TARGET USER OF THE CONSORTIUM, INNO4CFIs COULD FORWARD THE REQUEST OF CONTACT TO THE IDENTIFIED STAKEHOLDER THAT COULD DECIDE AUTONOMOUSLY TO GET IN TOUCH OR NOT WITH THE REQUESTER. THE DATA WILL BE SHARED ONLY UNDER EXPRESSED CONSENSUS.
2	TARGET USERS CONTACTS COLLECTION	N	THE COLLECTION OF THESE TYPES OF CONTACTS COMING FROM PROFESSIONALS WILL BE DONE ON A VOLUNTARY BASIS. HOWEVER, INNO4CFIs CONSORTIUM IS NOT ENTITLED TO PUBLISH THEM DUE TO POTENTIAL MISUSE CAUSED BY AUTOMATED SPAM PROGRAMS.	THE STATISTICAL INFORMATION ON THE STAKEHOLDER DATA (SUCH AS HOW MANY, FROM WHICH COUNTRIES, WHICH PROFESSIONS ETC.) CAN BE INTEGRATED IN A DETAILED REPORT IN AN AGGREGATED WAY TO AVOID INDIVIDUAL SPECIFICATION. ALSO, IF REQUESTED BY AN EXTERNAL PARTY OR STAKEHOLDER OF THE CONSORTIUM, INNO4CFIs COULD FORWARD THE REQUEST OF CONTACT TO THE IDENTIFIED USERS THAT COULD DECIDE AUTONOMOUSLY TO GET IN TOUCH OR NOT WITH THE REQUESTER. THE DATA WILL BE SHARED ONLY UNDER EXPRESSED CONSENT.
3	BUSINESS DATA OF THE TARGET USERS	N	THE COLLECTION OF THESE TYPES OF DATA IS DONE ON A VOLUNTARY BASIS OF THE SMEs APPLYING TO THE INNO4CFIs FSTP. HOWEVER, THE INNO4CFIs CONSORTIUM IS NOT ENTITLED TO PUBLISH THEM DUE TO MARKET AND INDUSTRIAL CONFIDENTIALITY.	THE STATISTICAL INFORMATION ON THE DATA (SUCH AS HOW MANY APPLICATIONS, FROM WHICH COUNTRIES, WHICH MARKET SEGMENT ETC.) CAN BE INTEGRATED IN A DETAILED REPORT IN AN AGGREGATED WAY TO AVOID INDIVIDUAL SPECIFICATION. THE DATA WILL BE SHARED ONLY UNDER EXPRESSED CONSENSUS.
4	NON-SENSITIVE PUBLISHABLE DATA (PUBLICATIONS AND BEST PRACTICES MANUAL)	Y	ACCESSIBLE DATA.	THE DATA COMING FROM THE RESEARCH PROJECT WILL BE ACCESSIBLE IN THE FORM OF PUBLICATIONS.
5	RECORDINGS OF THE EVENTS, INTERVIEWS OR MEETINGS	Y	ACCESSIBLE DATA.	THE DATA COMING FROM THE ACTIVITIES OF THE PROJECT WILL BE ACCESSIBLE IN VIDEO FORMAT OR IN WRITING.
6	DATA REPOSITORY FOR INTERNAL PROJECT MANAGEMENT (DELIVERABLES, REPORTS, RESULTS, MAILING LIST OF INNO4CFIs CONTACTS)	Y, UPON CONDITIONS.	THE COLLECTION OF THESE TYPES OF DATA WILL COME FROM THE MANAGEMENT OF THE PROJECT FOR IMPLEMENTATION PURPOSES. HOWEVER, THE INNO4CFIs CONSORTIUM IS NOT ENTITLED TO PUBLISH MAILING LIST CONTACTS DUE TO POTENTIAL MISUSE CAUSED BY AUTOMATED SPAM PROGRAMS. THE DATA COMING FROM DELIVERABLES, REPORTS, RESULTS	ALL DATA RELATED TO DELIVERABLES, REPORTS, RESULTS IDENTIFIED AS PUBLIC WILL BE ACCESSIBLE. IF MAILING CONTACTS ARE REQUESTED BY AN EXTERNAL PARTY OR STAKEHOLDER OR TARGET USER OF THE CONSORTIUM, INNO4CFIs COULD FORWARD THE REQUEST OF CONTACT TO THE IDENTIFIED CONTACT THAT COULD DECIDE AUTONOMOUSLY TO GET IN TOUCH OR NOT WITH THE REQUESTER. THE DATA WILL BE SHARED ONLY UNDER EXPRESSED

			WILL BE PUBLISHED UNLESS IPRs ARISE.	CONSENT.
7	VALIDATION DATA	Y, UPON CONDITIONS.	DATA WILL BE SHARED IN ORDER TO ENHANCE PROJECT SCALING UP. INDUSTRIAL RESEARCH OUTPUTS WILL BE EXPLOITED FOR INTERNAL PURPOSES EXCLUSIVELY.	POSSIBILITY OF ELABORATING AND DELIVERING A REPORT ON THE VALIDATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF THE FINAL SOLUTION BASED ON THE VALIDATION.
8	ENVIRONMENTAL, SOCIAL AND ECONOMIC IMPACT	N	ALL DATA COLLECTED VIA THE PROJECT WILL BE USED FOR THE DEPLOYMENT OF THE FINAL MODEL. HOWEVER, IN THE CASE OF PRIVATE DATA OR DATA COVERED BY IPRs IT WILL BE DIFFERENTIATED AND USED ONLY UNDER THE EXPRESSED CONSENSUS.	ALTHOUGH THE DATA COLLECTED BY THESE ACTIVITIES DO NOT INFRINGE PRIVACY AND SECURITY STANDARDS AND RULES, IF THERE IS NO DISAGREEMENT, THE DATA WILL BE PARTIALLY PUBLISHED (FOR EXAMPLE BY PROVIDING AN EXTRACT) BUT WILL BE USED TO DEVELOP THE FINAL MODEL AND AS SUCH PARTIAL DATA WILL BE SHARED ONLY AFTER IPRs PROCEDURE IS CONCLUDED.
9	TECHNOLOGY INTEGRATION DATA	N	THE COLLECTION AND ELABORATION OF THESE TYPES OF DATA COMES FROM INTERNAL RESEARCH AND EXPERTISE OF THE PARTNERS AND CAN BE SHARED OUTSIDE ONLY ONCE THE IPRs PROCEDURE IS CONCLUDED.	THE INFORMATION ON THE TECHNOLOGY INTEGRATION DATA CAN BE INTEGRATED IN A DETAILED REPORT IN AN AGGREGATED WAY. PARTIAL DATA WILL BE SHARED ONLY AFTER IPRs PROCEDURE IS CONCLUDED.
10	QUALITATIVE AND QUANTITATIVE RESOURCE INCREASE	Y, UPON CONDITIONS.	THE DATA FROM VALIDATION OF TECHNOLOGIES WILL BE PUBLISHED TO THE EXTENT IN WHICH IT DOES NOT REVEAL ANY EXISTING KNOW-HOW RELATED TO THE PROTECTION OF INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY.	A REPORT ON THE VALIDATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF THE FINAL SOLUTIONS BASED ON THE VALIDATION WILL BE CONVENIENTLY DELIVERED.
11	VALIDATION CYCLES DATA	Y, UPON CONDITIONS.		
12	MULTI-PARAMETERS FIELD DATA ACQUISITION	Y, UPON CONDITIONS.	DATA WILL BE SHARED IN ORDER TO ENHANCE PROJECT SCALING UP. INDUSTRIAL RESEARCH OUTPUTS WILL BE EXPLOITED FOR INTERNAL PURPOSES EXCLUSIVELY.	ALL OF THE DATA COLLECTED VIA TECHNOLOGY RELATED EXPERIMENTS, FIELD STUDIES AND INDUSTRIAL RESEARCH WILL PROVIDE THE CONTENT OF THE FINAL EXPLOITATION PLAN.

All research data will be made available for verification and re-use unless the task leader can justify why data cannot be made openly accessible. The final decision will be made based on an examination of the following elements regarding the confidentiality of datasets:

- (i) Commercial sensitivity of datasets.
- (ii) Data confidentiality for security reasons.
- (iii) Conflicts between open-access rules and national and European legislation (e.g. data protection regulations).

(iv) Sharing data would jeopardise the aims of the project.

(v) Other legitimate reasons, to be validated by the consortium partners.

Confidentiality: Each partner will treat information from other partners as confidential unless otherwise stated and will not disclose it to third parties unless the information is publicly available.

Open access to publications: Any proposed publication or communication by one of the parties is required to be submitted to other beneficiaries for their consent. All publications will be either gold or green open access in accordance with the Horizon Europe requirements.

Open Access to Data: Task leaders will notify the partnership of their planned intent to upload datasets to open-access repositories following approval of data for such purpose by the IPC.

Pre-existing know-how: Each partner is and remains the sole owner of its IPR over its pre-existing know-how. The partners will identify and list in the Consortium agreement the Pre-Existing Know-How over which they may grant access rights for the project. The partners agree that the Access Rights to the Pre-existing Know-How needed for carrying out their work under the project shall be granted on a royalty-free basis.

Ownership and protection of Foreground: The ownership of foreground will belong to the partner(s) generating it. Protection will be done appropriately. When the Foreground is the result of a work carried out by two or more partners and their respective share of the work cannot be ascertained, joint ownership will be agreed between the partners as it is established in the Internal agreement. If a partner wishes to assign any knowledge to a third party, it should do so, while observing the conditions set out in the INNO4CFIs Grant Agreement, and should inform the other partners and request their consent, which should not unreasonably be withheld.

Access Rights: Partners grant to each other royalty-free access rights to knowledge generated in the project and to the background knowledge they bring to the project to the extent needed to successfully perform the project tasks allocated to them.

Patents: Partners who own knowledge suitable for patent are obliged to make applications for patents or similar forms of protection and shall supply details of such application to the other partners. Information relating to patents that have been registered must be submitted under the 'IPR' section of the EU Participant Portal.

Use and dissemination: If dissemination of knowledge does not adversely affect its protection or use and is subject to legitimate interests, the partners shall ensure further dissemination of their knowledge as provided under the Grant Agreement and the Consortium agreement which is signed by all partners.

2.3 MAKING DATA INTEROPERABLE

The data resulting from INNO4CFIs will be partially interoperable, thus allowing data exchange and re-use between affiliated researchers, SMEs, and large companies operating in the same or adjacent field. Only the use of raw data will be subject to a different level of consent (only research use and sharing among partnership members;

public data in anonymous form, therefore without indication of name, surname, address and other data that could lead to revealing the identity of the data owner and provider).

The data outcomes of INNO4CFIs, and the present Data Management Plan will be constantly updated by the members of the consortium.

2.4 INCREASE DATA RE-USE

In order to provide documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use, INNO4CFIs will identify a proper methodology from the start of the success cases and go-to-business scenario and needs for low-moderate innovation regions guided by consortium member NTUA University. The provenance of the data will also be thoroughly documented according to high-level standards. According to TABLE 1, 2 and 3, the different types of data will be made freely and openly accessible in the public domain to permit proper re-use in line with the Grant Agreement and the Consortium Agreement obligations. After the end of the project part of the produced data during INNO4CFIs implementation will be usable by third-parties that could access and use them freely.

To reduce risks, data exploration should be done phase by phase. Commonly every single phase of exploration will have a different purpose, method, and data collected. Understanding the data exploration processes, activities and what kind of data is collected and/or required for every stage will be important to design and improve the database system itself. In addition, the data exploration evaluation will rely more on digital data processing.

All aspects related to addressing research outputs are duly considered in the present document in section 4 (allocation of resources), section 5 (data security) and section 6 (ethics).

3. OTHER RESEARCH OUTPUT

At the release of the present DMP, no other research outputs are foreseen and consequently no further details are available. However, INNO4CFIs is committed to consider and plan for the management of other research outputs that may be generated or re-used throughout the INNO4CFIs project development. In case other research outputs and requests for management and FAIR data use, reuse, sharing arise, all updates will be part of the second release of the DMP due in M18.

4. ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES

The INNO4CFIs partnership will exploit its website and the F6S platform dedicated to the INNO4CFIs project as the open accessible repository for making some data accessible (e.g. Open Call for the FSTP). Moreover, the publications, video recordings, and analysis of the training and the workshops will be published there. This will ensure that the data are safely stored in this certified repository for long-term preservation

and curation. The handling of the website and INNO4CFIs platform that is also used as a repository on behalf of INNO4CFIs fall under the responsibility of the Dissemination & Communications responsible partner (CIRCONNECT) while all data management issues related to the project rely on the project coordinator (FEA). As for the publications, where the analyses of the research data will be presented, the partnership will publish them in scientific journals that allow open access.

The costs related to above mentioned tools as well as publications in open access are claimed as part of the Horizon Europe grant and are reported in the Grant Agreement (budget section).

5. DATA SECURITY

As part of the above principles, a guideline for data protection and security of the INNO4CFIs project has been established in this section with the aim of ensuring that all researchers keep up the principles of lawful and ethical data management along with the whole project lifecycle. The guidelines established in this DMP are embraced within the partnership and the project management will ensure these principles will be followed. It is important to highlight that, because of the fact that the first version of this DMP was published before the start of the project's activities, there are still many uncertainties about the data collected in INNO4CFIs. As a result, additional details can be provided during the project's progress.

A list of data security topics is presented and elaborated below:

- *Purpose limitation and data minimisation* - Researchers will apply the principles of purpose limitation and data minimisation to the different types of data. Each researcher will take care not to collect any data that is outside the scope of their research and will not collect additional information not directly related to the goal of their research.
- *Personal Information* - As soon as the parameters are identified, the researchers need to indicate whether the dataset will contain personal information. In cases where the parameters themselves contain no personal information, but the various parameters can be merged to show a distinct pattern that can be linked to a specific person, the dataset is co-called pseudo-anonymized and will be classified as containing personal information as well. When the dataset contains personal information or otherwise information that needs to be kept confidential, the following privacy principles should be taken into account:
 - Sensitive data should be stored at either the dedicated trial site server or in a common code repository.
 - In the case of personal data collected in physical form (e.g., on paper), it shall be stored in a restricted-access area (e.g., GD restricted folder) to which only INNO4CFIs authorised staff has access. This applies to informed consent collected in paper form or documents generated along with the user requirements phase (e.g., results of the brainstorm with the users). Once the data has been digitised, the physical copies shall be securely destroyed.
- *Anonymisation and pseudo-anonymisation* - The data controller will make sure the personal data is anonymised as quickly as possible after its collection. When

the data cannot be anonymised completely, it will be pseudo-anonymised as much as possible – the personal identifier must be stored separately. The authorised personnel, data controllers, will store the key between the pseudo-anonymised files and the list of participants. The key will be stored in a separate physical location from the original files. It is kept in mind that the research subjects should be able to withdraw their data completely from INNO4CFIs at any point in time, hence the key must be stored securely but be feasible to be accessed.

- *Informed Consent* - When collecting personal information, consortium members are required to get informed consent from the participants which will be provided during each event/activity organised in the frame of the INNO4CFIs project.
- *End User's rights* - The user can submit a request to see which information about him/her is being kept on INNO4CFIs files through the contact person on the consent form. He/she can request to delete his/her information at any time. Furthermore, he/she can request that no additional data collection will take place starting immediately from the time of the request.
- *Storage and researchers' access to data* - Personal and sensitive user data will be stored safely and in a secure environment. A common security protocol will be established once the project reaches the maturity level, for all the partners storing personal data (defining authentication, authorisation and encryption; protection against unauthorised access, internal threats and human errors, etc.). Access to this secure environment can be granted or revoked by either the researchers responsible for the data or the project management on a case-to-case basis and will not be given out by default to all researchers contributing to INNO4CFIs activities. All users who are granted access to the datasets will need to sign a Data Protection Contract. Access can be restricted or revoked when researchers are not complying with the guidelines or when their contract is over.
- *Privacy Statement* - INNO4CFIs will actively communicate the privacy and security measures it takes through all media channels (from consent forms to websites) with a privacy statement. The statement will be adjusted to fit the target group, purpose, and level of privacy.
- *Update of the DMP* - The DMP is a living document. The fact that at the moment there are still many uncertainties about the data does not release the consortium from the obligation to ethically and lawfully collect, process, and store this data. All researchers have the responsibility to keep the DMP up to date, so the DMP will reflect the latest developments in data collection.

6. ETHICS

INNO4CFIs activities DO NOT foresee data collection such as health, sexual lifestyle, ethnicity, political opinion, religious or philosophical conviction.

However, INNO4CFIs involves 2 ethical issues:

- Humans, because it foresees activities involving work with human beings that are not part of the staff of the participants and covers research on or study of participants, persons concerned by the project activities.

- Personal Data, because it foresees research activities that involve the processing of personal data, such as interviews, surveys and questionnaires.

1. HUMANS

INNO4CFIs involves human participants as volunteers. In order to address this issue, INNO4CFIs will comply with the ethics provisions of the Grant Agreement, and will implement notably the highest ethical standards and the applicable international, EU and national law. INNO4CFIs will obtain the necessary ethics approvals and the free and fully informed consent of the participants. The target participants are entirely voluntary and INNO4CFIs will obtain and clearly document participants' informed consent in advance.

All participants will be given a project-specific informed consent form and detailed information sheets that:

- are written in a language and in terms they can fully understand;
- describe the aims, methods, and implications of the project activity, the nature of the participation and any benefits, risks or discomfort that might ensue;
- explicitly state that participation is voluntary and that anyone has the right to refuse to participate and to withdraw their participation or data at any time — without any consequences.

INNO4CFIs will ensure that potential participants have fully understood the information and do not feel pressured or coerced into giving consent, organising a session to explain the output of the research and the use of the data. INNO4CFIs will make sure that participants give their consent in writing, providing and explaining the informed consent form and information sheets that will be requested to be signed. Since the project involves studies using particular methodological tools (i.e., surveys, questionnaires, interviews, recordings), INNO4CFIs will clarify the ethical implications of the chosen methodologies to all the volunteers in a dedicated session providing all the information required and in writing. In addition, when conducting surveys and interviews that foresee the gathering and storage of personal information, INNO4CFIs foresees analyzing this aspect with the organisation's data protection officer. This aspect is deepened and analysed in subsection 2 of this paragraph (read below).

INNO4CFIs will make sure to keep on file copies of informed consent forms and information sheets.

INNO4CFIs does not involve: healthy volunteers for medical studies; patients for medical studies; potentially vulnerable individuals or groups; children/minors, persons unable to give informed consent.

INNO4CFIs does not involve interventions on the study participants, nor invasive techniques nor collection of biological samples. INNO4CFIs does not involve conducting a clinical study as defined by the Clinical Trial Regulation 536/2014.

2. PERSONAL DATA

INNO4CFIs does not foresee the collection of sensitive data. However, INNO4CFIs foresees research activities that involve processing of personal data, such as interviews, surveys, and questionnaires. In order to address this issue, INNO4CFIs will comply with the ethics provisions of the Grant Agreement, and will implement notably the highest ethical standards and the applicable international, EU, and national law. In

particular, personal data will be processed in accordance with certain principles and conditions that aim to limit the negative impact on the persons concerned and ensure fairness, transparency and accountability of the data processing, data quality and confidentiality. This implies that INNO4CFIs will follow these main obligations:

- The data processing should be subject to appropriate safeguards.
- Wherever and whenever possible the data will be processed in anonymised or pseudonymised form.
- Data processing will be done only subject to free and fully informed consent of the persons concerned.
- Data processing will not be performed in secret and participants/data subjects will always be made aware that they take part in the project and are informed of their rights and the potential risks that the data processing may bring.
- Information about the data processing operations and the contact details of the data protection officer (project DPO or partner DPO) will be provided to the participants (article 13/article 14 GDPR).
- The data will be processed only if it is really adequate, relevant, and limited to what is necessary for the project according to the 'data minimisation principle'.

In order to mitigate issues concerning the protection of personal data, INNO4CFIs will implement the following:

- Project specific data protection policy and/or the contact details of the data protection officer will be provided to all the volunteer participants.
- The security measures to prevent unauthorized access to personal data will be implemented in accordance with the DPO.
- All details of the informed consent procedures with regard to the data processing, including information on how to withdraw consent, will be provided beforehand to all the volunteers participants in written and during a dedicated session. Informed consent will be signed by the volunteers' participants and provided under request.
- Explanation as to how all of the processed data is relevant and limited to the purposes of the project will be provided beforehand to all the volunteers participants in written and during a dedicated session.
- Justification of why personal data will not be anonymised/pseudonymised will be provided beforehand to all the volunteer participants in written and during a dedicated session.
- Details of the data transfers (type of data transferred and country to which data are transferred) will be provided beforehand to all the volunteers participants in written and during a dedicated session.

INNO4CFIs also foresees the elaboration and issue of a Data Management Plan to be issued in month 3, 18, 36 as assigned deliverables.

INNO4CFIs does not involve: the processing of special categories of personal data; profiling, systematic monitoring of individuals, or processing of large scale of special categories of data or intrusive methods of data processing; further processing of previously collected personal data; exporting of personal data from the EU to non-EU countries; importing of personal data (data transfer) from non-EU countries into the EU or from a non-EU country to another non-EU country; processing of personal data related to criminal convictions or offences.

7. OTHER ISSUES

At the release of the present DPM, no other issues have been identified.

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